

CODEN [USA]: IAJ PBB

ISSN: 2349-7750

**INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES**Available online at: <http://www.iajps.com>

Research Article

**ANALYSIS OF BIOCHEMICAL PROFILE AND DIAGNOSTIC
ACCURACY OF ACUTE APPENDICITIS PATIENTS**Dr. Ahmed Muaaz Umer¹, Dr. Muhammad Saim Ashiq¹, Dr. Waleed Anwaar¹¹Nishtar Hospital Multan.

Article Received: March 2019

Accepted: April 2019

Published: May 2019

Abstract:

Introduction: Diagnosis of acute appendicitis remains a problem in pediatric surgery. Despite the fact that it is one of the most common surgical emergencies in children, the methods for diagnosing acute appendicitis have significantly not changed over the past few decades.

Objectives of the study: The main objective of the study is to analyze the biochemical profile and diagnostic accuracy of acute appendicitis patients.

Methodology of the study: This descriptive study was conducted in Nishtar Hospital, Multan during March 2018 to November 2018. This study was done with the permission of ethical committee of hospital. This study include data from 50 patient's age range 5 to 15 years old. Clinical signs of acute appendicitis determined by the surgeon and duration of symptoms were documented on admission. Blood samples for routine laboratory tests (white blood cell count, differential count, and C-reactive protein) and an additional 1.0 mL of blood for later analysis of IL-6 concentration were obtained on admission.

Results: The data was collected from 50 patients of both genders. There were no negative appendectomies during the study. Sixteen of 50 cases with acute appendicitis resulted in perforation. Significant differences between acute appendicitis and abdominal pain were seen in the following diagnostic tests: clinical signs, white blood cell count, serum C-reactive protein, IL-6 concentrations, and ultrasonography. White blood cell counts, serum C-reactive protein, and IL-6 concentrations in children with acute appendicitis were dependent on the duration of symptoms.

Conclusion: It is concluded that clinical signs were still the most sensitive diagnostic method. Among laboratory tests, white blood cell count and C-reactive protein concentration in serum are of low diagnostic accuracy and have only a supportive role in diagnosing acute appendicitis in children.

Corresponding author:

Ahmed Muaaz Umer,
Nishtar Hospital Multan.

QR code

Please cite this article in press Ahmed Muaaz Umer et al., *Analysis of Biochemical Profile and Diagnostic Accuracy of Acute Appendicitis Patients.*, Indo Am. J. P. Sci, 2019; 06(05).

INTRODUCTION:

Diagnosis of acute appendicitis remains a problem in pediatric surgery. Despite the fact that it is one of the most common surgical emergencies in children, the methods for diagnosing acute appendicitis have significantly not changed over the past few decades. Clinical examination and laboratory parameters, such as white blood cell, differential counts (percentage of neutrophil granulocytes and band neutrophil granulocytes), and C-reactive protein were the only diagnostic tools for many years [1]. Perforation rate was high, as well as the number of negative appendectomies. Following the introduction of ultrasonography in the last two decades and computed tomography (CT) in the last decade, the rate of negative appendectomies in children has decreased [2], but the perforation rate has remained high (22%-62%). Therefore, an ideal diagnostic method or a combination of laboratory, clinical, and imaging methods is still being sought [3].

Diagnosis of AA is one of the most common dilemmas which surgeons encounter in the emergency room. The typical clinical picture, with pain migration towards the right lower quadrant of the abdomen or signs of localized peritonitis, is unfortunately found in much less patients than it is thought. On the other hand, too much reliance on laboratory findings can misguide a surgeon's diagnosis. Broad differential diagnoses, especially in women, and an unclear clinical picture can frustrate a surgeon, leading him to order a Multislice Computed Tomography (MSCT) [4]. However, although MSCT of the abdomen very accurately recognizes AA, it uses a high dosage of harmful radiation which makes it absolutely unacceptable for routine use in patients suspected of having appendicitis. Acute appendicitis is the most common cause of emergency abdominal surgery [5]. The diagnosis remains a significant challenge due to varying symptoms and signs which may mimic other conditions. A delayed diagnosis can lead to significant complications such as perforation, abscess formation, peritonitis and death. The standard treatment is surgical removal of the in-flamed appendix. Conservative management with anti-microbial therapy

for early uncomplicated appendicitis is controversial due to increased failure rates [6].

Objectives of the study:

The main objective of the study is to analyze the biochemical profile and diagnostic accuracy of acute appendicitis patients.

Methodology of the study:

This descriptive study was conducted in Nishtar Hospital, Multan during March 2018 to November 2018. This study was done with the permission of ethical committee of hospital. This study include data from 50 patient's age range 5 to 15 years old. Clinical signs of acute appendicitis determined by the surgeon and duration of symptoms were documented on admission. Blood samples for routine laboratory tests (white blood cell count, differential count, and C-reactive protein) and an additional 1.0 mL of blood for later analysis of IL-6 concentration were obtained on admission. Abdominal ultrasonography was performed in patients. It was not done in children with evident clinical signs of diffuse peritonitis (diffuse abdominal rigidity and clinical deterioration) who were taken to the operating room immediately after admission.

Statistical analysis:

The data was collected and analyzed using SPSS version 21.0. Data were presented as median and range for numeric data and as counts (%) for categorical data.

RESULTS:

The data was collected from 50 patients of both genders. There were no negative appendectomies during the study. Sixteen of 50 cases with acute appendicitis resulted in perforation. Significant differences between acute appendicitis and abdominal pain were seen in the following diagnostic tests: clinical signs, white blood cell count, serum C-reactive protein, IL-6 concentrations, and ultrasonography. White blood cell counts, serum C-reactive protein, and IL-6 concentrations in children with acute appendicitis were dependent on the duration of symptoms.

Table 01: Biochemical profile of selected patients

Diagnostic method	acute appendicitis	abdominal pain	P
Duration of symptoms (h)	24.0 (4.0-168.0)	24.0 (2.0-120.0)	0.577 [‡]
Clinical signs:			
positive	46	22	0.002 [§]
negative	3	11	
WBC (x10 ⁹ /L)	15.1 (5.9-31.6)	10.6 (4.7-25.5)	0.008
Neutrophil granulocytes (%)	76 (54-91)	73 (40-93)	0.328
Band neutrophil granulocytes (%)	4 (0-24)	0 (0-14)	0.105 [‡]
CRP (mg/L)	21.0 (5.0-137.0)	9.0 (5.0-148.0)	0.038 [‡]
IL-6 (ng/L)	11.8 (5.0-1000.0)	5.0 (2.0-59.2)	<0.001 [‡]
Ultrasonography:			
positive	32 TP	1 FP	<0.001 [§]
negative	3 FN	20 TN	
not assessed	14	12	

DISCUSSION:

The laboratory test for acute appendicitis in the children with the highest diagnostic accuracy in our study was the inflammatory marker IL-6. Its diagnostic accuracy in the adult population is controversial. Several studies in adults were unable to confirm the usefulness of IL-6 for diagnosing acute appendicitis, while others, including studies in children, found it to be a useful marker [7]. The differences in the studies could be attributed to different study populations and designs. Some authors included only operated patients, while others included all admitted patients [8]. All patients with known infection other than acute appendicitis and mesenteric lymphadenitis were excluded from our study. This could result in lower IL-6 levels in the abdominal pain group and consequently improve the diagnostic accuracy of IL-6 in our study, as IL-6 is a non-specific marker of inflammation [9]. Similar to our findings, Pajaanen et al reported that the preoperative diagnostic accuracy of IL-6 in adults operated for acute appendicitis, determined by the area under the ROC curve, was higher than that of white blood cell count and C-reactive protein. Recently, two studies of IL-6 in children have been published [10]. The first showed that determination of the serum IL-6 concentration on admission was of no diagnostic value. The second showed that the determination of IL-6 6 hours after admission reached the highest accuracy rate, compared with white blood cell count and tumor necrosis factor- α (TNF- α). The second study showed that IL-6 correlated significantly with the severity of appendiceal inflammation, but the diagnostic usefulness of the difference between IL-6 and C-reactive protein was not significant [11].

CONCLUSION:

It is concluded that clinical signs were still the most sensitive diagnostic method. Among laboratory tests, white blood cell count and C-reactive protein concentration in serum are of low diagnostic accuracy and have only a supportive role in diagnosing acute appendicitis in children.

REFERENCES:

1. Jones K, Pena AA, Dunn EL, Nadalo L, Mangram AJ. Are negative appendectomies still acceptable? *Am J Surg.* 2004;188:748–54.
2. Ponsky TA, Huang ZJ, Kittle K, Eichelberger MR, Gilbert JC, Brody F, et al. Hospital- and patient-level characteristics and the risk of appendiceal rupture and negative appendectomy in children. *JAMA.* 2004;292:1977–82.
3. Nwomeh BC, Chisolm DJ, Caniano DA, Kelleher KJ. Racial and socioeconomic disparity in perforated appendicitis among children: where is the problem? *Pediatrics.* 2006;117:870–5.
4. Andersson RE. Meta-analysis of the clinical and laboratory diagnosis of appendicitis. *Br J Surg.* 2004;91:28–37.
5. Eriksson S, Granstrom L, Olander B, Wretling B. Sensitivity of interleukin-6 and C-reactive protein concentrations in the diagnosis of acute appendicitis. *Eur J Surg.* 1995;161:41–5.
6. Yoon DY, Chu J, Chandler C, Hiyama S, Thompson JE, Hines OJ. Human cytokine levels in nonperforated versus perforated appendicitis: molecular serum markers for extent of disease? *Am Surg.* 2002;68:1033–7.
7. Gurleyik G, Gurleyik E, Cetinkaya F, Unalmiser S. Serum interleukin-6 measurement in the

- diagnosis of acute appendicitis. ANZ J Surg. 2002;72:665–7.
8. Erkasap S, Ates E, Ustuner Z, Sahin A, Yilmaz S, Yasar B, et al. Diagnostic value of interleukin-6 and C-reactive protein in acute appendicitis. Swiss Surg. 2000;6:169–72.
 9. Paajanen H, Mansikka A, Laato M, Ristamaki R, Pulkki K, Kostiaainen S. Novel serum inflammatory markers in acute appendicitis. Scand J Clin Lab Invest. 2002;62:579–84.
 10. Turkyilmaz Z, Sonmez K, Karabulut R, Elbeg S, Moralioglu S, Demirtola A, et al. Sequential cytokine levels in the diagnosis of appendicitis. Scand J Clin Lab Invest. 2006;66:723–31.
 11. Sack U, Biereder B, Elouahidi T, Bauer K, Keller T, Trobs RB. Diagnostic value of blood inflammatory markers for detection of acute appendicitis in children. BMC Surg. 2006;6:15.